
The following is an English translation of the presentation titled "A Unified Explanation of the Gestalt Laws by Synchronous Oscillations of Figure Strength," delivered in Japanese by Sohmiya Tamotsu at the 40th Annual Convention of the Japanese Psychological Association, held at Chukyo University on September 29, 1976.

The content of this presentation is based on the book "Fundamental study on pattern recognition by a new experimental method" by Tamotsu Somiya & Kazuko Sohmiya (National Diet Library Digital Collections — DOI: 10.11501/12628158), which was distributed starting on the same day.

This translation aims to preserve the terminology and theoretical framework of the original 1976 presentation as closely as possible.

The term "figure strength" is a translation of the author's original concept of *zukeisei no tsuyosa* (図形性の強さ), which is defined in this paper as a function of the disappearance rate obtained by the suppression method.

The Japanese term *shuhenkou* (周辺光) refers to the illumination or reflected light surrounding the test figure — roughly equivalent to "Ground effect." So, it is translated here as "Ground effect." However, the two terms are not strictly equivalent. For a fuller explanation, please refer to the Translator's Note at the end of this text.

The abbreviations TF (Test Figure) and SF (Suppression Figure) are retained throughout the translation following the notation used in the original presentation.

Perception M-96

A Unified Explanation of the Gestalt Laws by Synchronous Oscillations of Figure Strength

SOHMIYA TAMOTSU

Wertheimer's (1923) Gestalt laws are an essential principle not only of visual perception but also of the fundamental characteristics of information-processing mechanisms in living organisms. Here, we quantitatively treat Gestalt characteristics by means of the concept of figure strength and, at the same time, propose a unified explanatory principle for them.

I Perceptual Grouping and Figure Strength

Factor of Proximity

The test figure (TF) for the left eye consisted of black circles 5 mm in diameter, drawn in black ink on white Kent paper and arranged horizontally with center-to-center distances of either 7.5 mm or 20 mm. The flickering figure for the right eye (SF) consisted of two black parallel lines 90 mm long, 10 mm apart, and 2 mm wide. The TF was adjusted so that its center coincided with the center of the SF.

The subjects were instructed to fixate point B and to report, immediately after each onset of the SF, whether dots A and B, or dots B and C, disappeared simultaneously and completely.

First, the disappearance rate (δ) of the TF was measured.

$$\delta = (\text{frequency of complete disappearance of TF}) / (\text{frequency of presentations of SF})$$

On the basis of the obtained δ value, the concept of figure strength (F) was introduced. Figure strength was defined as $F = \log (1/\delta)$ (see Management Guide, 1975).

As shown in Fig. 1, the F value of the pair perceived as grouped (for example, dots A and B) is minimal.

Fig.1 Factor of proximity and figure strength

Fig.2 Factor of similarity and figure strength

Factor of Similarity

The TF was a geometric figure consisting of black filled circles and black outline circles, each 5 mm in diameter, arranged horizontally at intervals of 10 mm. The SF consisted of the same parallel lines used in the experiment on proximity.

As shown in Fig. 2, the F values of the pairs perceived as grouped (dots A and B, and dots C and D) are smaller than that of the pair not perceived as grouped (dots B and C).

Furthermore, the F values of the grouped pairs are smaller than the F value of each single dot.

Factor of Closure

The TF was a partial geometric figure consisting of an outline square with sides 10 mm in length and a lens-shaped figure 10 mm in length. The SF consisted of two black parallel lines whose interval was widened to 12 mm. As shown in Fig. 3, the F values of the square and the lens-shaped figure, which are easily perceived as grouped, are minimal.

<p>Stimulus</p>	<p>0.85</p>	<p>0.74</p>	<p>1.40</p>	<p>2.40</p>	<p>1.22</p>	<p>2.70</p>	<p>2.70</p>
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Fig.3 Factor of closure and figure strength

Factor of Good Continuity

The TF was a partial geometric figure consisting of a slanting line 20 mm in length and a sine-wave figure having a total length of 40 mm and a wave height of 6 mm. The slanting line intersected the sine-wave figure. The SF consisted of two black parallel lines 90 mm long, 20 mm

apart, and 2 mm wide. As shown in Fig. 4, the F values of the line segment A+B and the sine-wave figure C+D, both of which are easily perceived as grouped, are minimal.

	A + B	C + D	A	C	A + C	B + C	A + C + D
Stimulus	0.52	0.66	0.85	0.89	0.92	1.00	1.30

Fig.4 Factor of good continuity and figure strength

Factor of Good Gestalt (Good form)

The TF consisted of a combination of an outline circle 14 mm in diameter and an outline diamond having a side length of 10 mm. The SF consisted of two black parallel lines 90 mm long, 15 mm apart, and 2 mm wide. As shown in Fig. 5, the F values of the circle (A+B) and the outline diamond (C+D), which are easily perceived as grouped, are minimal.

	A + B	C + D	A + D	B + C	B + D	A + C	A	C
Stimulus	0.59	0.77	1.15	1.22	1.70	2.00	2.30	2.15

Fig.5 Factor of good Gestalt and figure strength

II Figure Strength Oscillates Periodically

Empirical Experiment 1

The TFs were black filled circles 3 mm and 10 mm in diameter, respectively. The SF was a black outline circle having an inner diameter of 10 mm and a line width of 1 mm. The TF and SF were adjusted so as to be concentric.

Figure 6 shows the temporal states of complete disappearance and appearance of the TF immediately after each onset of the SF.

The disappearance rate of the 3-mm black circle was 20%, whereas that of the 10-mm black circle was 78%.

However, although the disappearance rates differed greatly, the disappearance phenomena in both figures showed clear periodicity.

(This periodicity of disappearance is a general characteristic commonly observed in all suppression experiments.)

Fig. 6 Temporal states of disappearance and appearance of the test figure during observation.

[Translator's note] In Figure 6, the test figure is drawn smaller under Condition II only for ease of illustration. In the actual experiment, the diameters of the TF and SF were identical.

Figure 7 explains the results shown in Figure 6 on the basis of the following postulates.

1. The figure strength of TF, which is presented continuously and for a long time, oscillates periodically.
2. The amplitude of oscillation increases with increasing the figure strength of TF.
3. The suppression strength of the intermittently presented SF depends on the maximum value of figure strength immediately after each appearance of SF.
4. The suppression strength of SF is a monotonic decreasing function of a distance between TF and SF. Hence, under Condition I
Suppression strength of SF under Condition I < Suppression strength of SF under Condition II
5. Ground effect is independent of figure effect and equal under Conditions I and II.
Hence,
Ground effect under Condition I = Ground effect under Condition II
[where Ground effect is suppression strength of ground]
6. TF disappears when the figure strength of TF < the suppression strength of SF and remains visible when the figure strength of TF > the suppression strength of SF.

Fig. 7. Explanation of suppression phenomena by means of periodic oscillations of figure strength

Thus, if the figure strength of the test figure oscillates periodically, the removal of the suppression factors, namely the "other-eye figure" alone (Fig. 8) or the "other-eye figure plus surrounding illumination" (Fig. 9), should produce the following phenomena.

That is, for the 3-mm circle, whose disappearance duration is short, when only the other-eye figure is removed, the probability of appearance depends upon the timing of removal:

1. Immediately after disappearance: the probability of appearance is extremely low.
2. One second after disappearance: the probability of appearance is high.

On the other hand, if the other-eye figure and the surrounding illumination are removed simultaneously, the test figure should appear regardless of the timing of removal.

A: Removal of the suppression strength of the SF

B: Removal of the suppression strength of (the SF+Ground)

Fig.8 Experimental paradigm for proving the periodicity of figure strength

Furthermore, for the 10-mm circle, whose disappearance duration is long, when only the other-eye figure is removed, the probability of appearance depends upon the timing of removal as follows:

1. Immediately after disappearance: probability of appearance = 100%.
2. One second after disappearance: probability of appearance decreases.
3. Two seconds after disappearance: probability of appearance = 0%.
4. Three seconds after disappearance: probability of appearance increases.
5. Four seconds after disappearance: probability of appearance = 100%.

Fig.9 Temporal sequence of suppression and non-suppression after each removal of two kinds of suppression effects; (SF + ground) or (only SF) .

In contrast, when both the other-eye figure and the surrounding illumination are removed, the test figure should always appear irrespective of the timing of removal.

Experiment 2

The TF was a black circle of either 3 mm or 10 mm in diameter. The SF was a black outline circle 10 mm in diameter with a line width of 1 mm.

Removal of the "other-eye figure" and removal of the "other-eye figure plus surrounding illumination" were carried out as follows.

For the 3-mm test figure, removal was performed immediately after disappearance and one second after disappearance.

For the 10-mm test figure, removal was performed immediately after disappearance and at 1, 2, 3, and 4 seconds after disappearance.

The results are shown in Table 1 and are in good agreement with the theoretical predictions.

Table 1. Temporal sequence of suppression and non-suppression as a function of timing of removal (The numeral values are the frequency of each view out of ten trials under the two conditions)

TF	Phenomena	Figure					Figure + Ground				
		Just after	After 1 sec.	After 2 sec.	After 3 sec.	After 4 sec.	Just after	After 1 sec.	After 2 sec.	After 3 sec.	After 4 sec.
3 mm circle	Suppression	8	1				0	0			
	Non-suppression	2	9				10	10			
10 mm circle	Suppression	0	4	10	7	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Non-suppression	10	6	0	3	10	10	10	10	10	10

III. Explanation of Perceptual Grouping by Synchronous Oscillations of Figure Strength

As shown in Figs. 1–5, when figures are perceived as grouped, their figure strength becomes smaller than in other modes of perception.

Figures 10 and 11 explain the factors of proximity and similarity on the basis of the synchronous oscillations of figure strength.

The explanation is based on the synchronization of the phases of the periodic oscillations of figure strength between adjacent figures.

As shown in the figures, the duration during which the figure strengths of both figures fall below the suppression level (L1) decreases in proportion to the phase difference between them.

On the other hand, when the phases become synchronized, this duration reaches its maximum.

Therefore, the figure strength, which is defined as the inverse function of the disappearance rate, becomes minimal when the phases are synchronized. Furthermore, the factors of closure, good continuity, and good Gestalt (good form), among others, are considered to be conditions that promote the synchronization of phases.

Fig.10 Explanation of the factor of proximity based on synchronous oscillations of figure

Fig.11 Explanation of the factor of similarity based on the synchronous oscillations of figure strength.

As described above, Gestalt characteristics have been explained by the synchronous oscillations of figure strength. Furthermore, **we propose that synchronous activity of the cerebral cortex constitutes the most fundamental principle underlying all mental activities of the human brain, including self-consciousness and self-identity** (June 3, 1976).

Note:

1. When two figures are placed in close proximity, the “ground” region between them begins to take on a perceptual quality resembling a “figure.” In other words, the ground abandons its intended passive role as mere background and instead assumes an active perceptual role. This phenomenon cannot be adequately explained by the traditional Gestalt figure-ground dichotomy alone. It is precisely because the author sought to challenge this conventional distinction that he deliberately avoided the Gestalt term “ground” and instead introduced the concept of shuhenkou (周辺光). In this translation, the term is rendered as “Ground effect” for this reason, though the two are not strictly equivalent.

2. In the original Japanese text, the SF is denoted by a unique symbol shown below. Based on the author’s earlier 1968 paper, in which the same symbol first appears, the rectangular frame appears to indicate that the enclosed figure functions as a suppression figure, while ‘IF’ stands for intermittent figure (点滅図形).

This symbol is replaced throughout this translation by the abbreviation SF (Suppression Figure).

3. The original author, Tamotsu Sohmiya, has passed away. This English translation has been prepared and uploaded by his son, Seiyu Sohmiya, for the purpose of wider academic dissemination and open-access availability (June 2, 2026).

4. This translation is not an isolated publication. It forms part of the research archive of Tamotsu Sohmiya and Kazuko Sohmiya, independent researchers who pursued studies of visual perception for approximately five decades.

Additional papers, conference proceedings, correspondence, unpublished manuscripts, and historical materials from the Sohmiya Archive are being prepared for future release.

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